

Lost Sanskrit Reconstruction, Translation and Commentary on the most difficult Buddhist Pali Sutra - Mulapariyayasutta

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Abstract:

The Mulapariyayasutta has the distinction of being the most dense, difficult, abstruse and complicated texts of the Pali Canon. While the translation of the lost Sanskrit original is preserved in Chinese, fragments of this lost Sanskrit manuscript have been found in Turfan, Central Asia. This paper is a reconstruction of the lost Sanskrit text of the ancient Mulaparyayasutra text.

This paper covers:

- The reconstructed Sanskrit text.
- The English translation of the Sanskrit text.
- Commentary on the Pali and Sanskrit text.
- Anglicized Pali text.

Keywords:

Mulapariyayasutta, Pali Canon, Pali Sutras, Gautama Buddha, Advaita Vedanta

Discussion:

Introduction (Sanskrit):

एवं मे श्रुतम्—

एकं समयं भगवान् उक्कट्ठायां विहरति सुभगवने सालराजमूले ।

तत्र खलु भगवान् भिक्षून् आमन्त्रयति — “भिक्षवः” इति ।

“भदन्ते” इति ते भिक्षवः भगवतः प्रत्यशृण्वन् ।

भगवान् एतद् अवोचत् —

“सर्वधर्ममूलपर्यायं वः, भिक्षवः, देशयिष्यामि ।

तत् शृणुत, साधुकं मनसि कुरुत, भाषिष्यामि” इति ।

“एवं, भन्ते” इति खलु ते भिक्षवः भगवतः प्रत्यशृण्वन् ।

भगवान् एतद् अवोचत् —

English Translation:

Thus (evam) I (me) heard (shrutham) —

(At) one (ekam) time (samayam), Bhagavan (Buddha) was dwelling (viharathi) at Ukkatha inside a forest (vane) named Subhaga, at the root (moole) of a majestic (raaj) Sal tree.

There indeed (tatra khalu), Bhagavan (Buddha) welcomed (aamantrayathi) the Bhikkus (saying) thus (iti) “O Bhikkus (Bhikkave).”

The Bhikkus responded (pratyashrunvan) to Bhagavan (Buddha), “O venerable one (bhidhante)” in this manner (iti).

Bhagavan (Buddha) said (avochath) this (etadh),

“(I will) teach you (deshyishyaami) comprehension (paryaay) of the root of all (sarva) Dharmas (moola) to you (vo).

I will lecture (bhaashishyaami) the following (iti), hear (shrenuth) that (iti) well (sadhakam) (and) try (kuruth) to understand (manasi).”

“Yes (evam), O venerable one (bhante)” thus (iti) indeed (khalu) the Bhikkus responded (pratyashrunvan) to Bhagavan (Buddha).

Bhagavan (Buddha) explained (avochath) the following (etadh):

Verse 1 (Sanskrit):

इह भिक्षवः अश्रुतवान् पृथग्जनः

आर्याणाम् अदर्शावी, आर्यधर्मस्य अकोविदः, आर्यधर्मे अविनीतः,

सत्पुरुषाणाम् अदर्शावी, सत्पुरुषधर्मस्य अकोविदः, सत्पुरुषधर्मे अविनीतः।

पृथिवीम् पृथिवीतः संजानाति, पृथिवीम् पृथिवीतः संज्ञात्वा
पृथिवीम् मन्यते, पृथिव्याः मन्यते, पृथिवीतः मन्यते, पृथिवीम् मेति मन्यते,
पृथिवीम् अभिनन्दति
तत् कस्य हेतु?
अपरिज्ञातं तस्याः इति वदामि

English Translation:

O Bhikku (bhikkave), these (iha) newcomer (puthu) people (jano)
having not heard the (Vedic) shruthis (ashruthvaan),
having not seen (adarshaavi) the Aryans (followers of Rta)
having not become skilled (akovidh) in the Dharma of the Aryans
having not become knowledgeable (avineeth) of the Dharma of the Aryans
having not seen (adarshaavi) the truth (sat) of the (Vedic) Purusha
having not become skilled (akovidh) in the Dharma of the Sattva (Guna) (Vedic) Purusha
having not become knowledgeable (avineeth) of the Dharma of the Sattva (Guna) (Vedic)
Purusha

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) earth (Prithveem) with respect to (other) earth (Pritiveeth),
having known (samgyaatva) earth (Prithveem) with respect to Prithvi (Pritiveeth),

(He) understands (manyathe) earth (Prithveem), understands (manyathe) (the produce) from
the earth (Prithivya), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the earth (Pritiveeth),
understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the earth (Prithveem),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the first Panchabhuta) the earth (Prithveem).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by
the knower).

Commentary:

There are notorious blunders made by Buddhist translators when translating the words like
“ashruthvaan,” “Aryan,” and “Satpurusha.” All these words have very important Vedic
connotations and all of that has been conveniently put aside by modern English translators.
These mistakes ignore the lived reality and the world of Gautama Buddha, who was trying to
convert Vedic seekers to his Sangha. Clearly, it would have made sense to use Vedic terms to
attract Vedic aspirants.

The word “ashruthvaan” refers to a person who has not heard the shrutis. It is mistakenly translated as unlearned, but it has a much deeper meaning. The person who has not heard the Shrutis is not truly learned. The word “shruthi” refers exclusively to the Vedas. Gautama Buddha was a proficient Vedic scholar, and he wanted his disciples to learn the Vedic connotations.

The word “Aryan” is a person who follows Dharma or Rta. The words “Dharma,” “Rta” and “Sat” all refer to the same Rta. Rta is translated as the order of the universe.

Sat Purusha does not mean true person. Purusha has a colloquial meaning of “person,” but it also refers to the Vedic Brahman. Sat can refer to Satya (truth) or Sattva (guna). Sat Purusha is the Purusha who lords over truth or the Purusha who lords over Sattva. We know that it refers to Lord Vishnu. Vishnu is the lord of Sattva, lord of Satya and the highest Purusha (Purushottaman).

Moving to the next section, Gautama Buddha makes fun of those people who identify closely with the objects of the sensory world.

He begins with the first Panchabhuta – Earth or Prithvi.

Those who think they understand the Panchabhuta (Prithvi) actually understand not the outer manifestation of that element, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside element as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He thinks that he knows how earth transforms into plants, but really has no idea. Every object on earth is but a modification of earth, but the fool cannot see the link. He sees everything as separate and distinct. The fool identifies some land as his and other land as belonging to others. All of this is foolish. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world.

This foolish person rejoices about life surrounded by the Panchabhuta (Prithvi), not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 2 (Sanskrit):

आपम् आपतः संजानाति, आपम् आपतः संज्ञात्वा
आपम् मन्यते, आपस्मिन् मन्यते, आपतः मन्यते, आपम् मेति मन्यते
आपम् अभिनन्दति
तत् कस्य हेतु?
अपरिज्ञातं तस्याः इति वदामि

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the divine waters (Aapam) with respect to the (other) divine waters (Aapatha), having known (samgyaatva) the divine waters (Aapam) with respect to the divine waters (Aapam),

(He) understands (manyathe) the divine waters (Aapam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the divine waters (Aapasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the divine waters (Aapam), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the divine waters (Aapam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the second Panchabhuta) the divine waters (Aapam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the second Panchabhuta – Divine waters or Aapa.

Those who think they understand the Panchabhuta (Aapa) actually understand not the outer manifestation of that element, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside element as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a world filled by the Panchabhuta (Aap), not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 3 (Sanskrit):

तेजम् तेजतः संजानाति ।

तेजम् तेजतः संज्ञात्वा

तेजम् मन्यते, तेजस्मिन् मन्यते, तेजतः मन्यते, तेजम् मेति मन्यते,

तेजम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the brilliant fire (Tejam) with respect to the (other) brilliant fire (Tejath), having known (samgyaatva) the divine waters (Tejam) with respect to the divine waters (Tejath),

(He) understands (manyathe) the brilliant fire (Tejam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the brilliant fire (Tejasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the brilliant fire (Tejam), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the brilliant fire (Tejam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the third Panchabhuta) the brilliant fire (Tejam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the third Panchabhuta – Fire or Tejas (meaning Agni).

Those who think they understand the Panchabhuta (Tejas) actually understand not the outer manifestation of that element, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside element as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a world filled by the Panchabhuta (Tejas), not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 4 (Sanskrit):

वायुम् वायुतः संजानाति ।
वायुम् वायुतः संज्ञात्वा
वायुम् मन्यते, वायुस्मिन् मन्यते, वायुतः मन्यते, वायुम् मेति मन्यते,
वायुम् अभिनन्दति ।
तत् कस्य हेतु ?
अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) air (Vayum) with respect to the (other) air (Vayuth), having known (samgyaatva) air (Vayum) with respect to air (Vayuth),

(He) understands (manyathe) air (Vayum), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in air (Vayuasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from air (Vayum), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) air (Vayum),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the fourth Panchabhuta) air (Vayum).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha then moves on to the fourth Panchabhuta – Air or Vayu.

Those who think they understand the Panchabhuta (Vayu) actually understand not the outer manifestation of that element, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside element as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a world filled by the Panchabhuta (Vayu), not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 5 (Sanskrit):

भूतं भूततः संजानाति ।

भूतं भूततः संज्ञात्वा

भूतं मन्यते, भूतेषु मन्यते, भूततः मन्यते, भूतं मेति मन्यते,

भूतम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) life (Bhutham) with respect to the (other) life (Bhutath), having known (samgyaatva) life (Bhutham) with respect to life (Bhutath),

(He) understands (manyathe) life (Bhutham), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) in life (Bhuteshu), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from life (Bhutath), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) life (Bhutham),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the first form of existence) life (Bhutham).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the first denizen of Atma Gyana – Bhu or earthly life.

Those who think they understand life (Bhu) actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes earthly life, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 6 (Sanskrit):

देवं देवतः संजानाति ।
देवं देवतः संज्ञात्वा
देवं मन्यते, देवेषु मन्यते, देवतः मन्यते, देवं मेति मन्यते,
देवम् अभिनन्दति ।
तत् कस्य हेतु ?
अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the Devas (Devam) with respect to the (other) Devas (Devath), having known (samgyaatva) the Devas (Devam) with respect to the Devas (Devath),

(He) understands (manyathe) Devas (Devam), understands (manyathe) (the forms) in the Devas (Deveshu), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the Devas (Devatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the Devas (Devam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the second form of existence) the Devas (Devam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the second denizen of Atma Gyana – the divine Devas.

Those who think they understand the Devas actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the Devas, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 7 (Sanskrit):

प्रजापतिं प्रजापतितः संजानाति ।

प्रजापतिं प्रजापतितः संज्ञात्वा

प्रजापतिं मन्यते, प्रजापतौ मन्यते, प्रजापतितः मन्यते, प्रजापतिं मेति मन्यते,

प्रजापतिम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathim) with respect to the (other) Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathith), having known (samgyaatva) Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathim) with respect to Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathith),

(He) understands (manyathe) Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathim), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathau), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathitha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathim),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the third form of existence) Prajapathi Brahma (Prajapathim).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the third denizen of Atma Gyana – Prajapathi Brahma.

Those who think they understand Prajapathi Brahma actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes Prajapathi Brahma, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 8 (Sanskrit):

ब्रह्मं ब्रह्मतः संजानाति ।

ब्रह्मं ब्रह्मतः संज्ञात्वा

ब्रह्मं मन्यते, ब्रह्मणि मन्यते, ब्रह्मतः मन्यते, ब्रह्मं मेति मन्यते,

ब्रह्मम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the Brahman (Brahmam) with respect to the (other) Brahman (Brahmatha), having known (samgyaatva) the Brahman (Brahmam) with respect to the Brahman (Brahmatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the Brahman (Brahmam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the Brahman (Brahmani), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the Brahman (Brahmatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the Brahman (Brahmam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the fourth form of existence) the Brahman (Brahmam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha then moves on to the fourth and final denizen of Atma Gyana – the Brahman. Note that Brahman used here is neutral in gender, indicating the Brahman rather than the masculine form that refers to Prajapathi Brahma. ब्रह्मं is a noun with stem being ब्रह्मन् (neuter). It is unforgivable to mix the masculine brahma with the neuter Brahman, This is a mistake which every Pali interpreter makes.

Those who think they understand the Brahman actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the Brahman, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct. The fool who thinks of Brahman as an object of achievement, will never find the Brahman.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 9 (Sanskrit):

आभास्वरे आभास्वतः संजानाति ।

आभास्वरे आभास्वतः संज्ञात्वा

आभास्वरे मन्यते, आभास्वरेषु मन्यते, आभास्वतः मन्यते, आभास्वरे मेति मन्यते,

आभास्वरम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) complete radiance (Aabhasvare) with respect to the (other) complete radiance (Aabhasavatha), having known (samgyaatva) complete radiance (Aabhasvare) with respect to complete radiance (Aabhasavatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) complete radiance (Aabhasvare), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in complete radiance (Aabhasvareshu), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from complete radiance (Aabhasavatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) complete radiance (Aabhasvare),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the first form of realization) complete radiance (Aabhasvare).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

आभास्वर is the Sanskrit original word. आभास्वर is आ (complete form, highest form) + √भास् (shining, radiance) + वर (possessing, endowed with).

Hence, आभास्वर refers to the complete radiance that begins to spread around the seeker. The goal of life is to follow the path of complete radiance and find the Atma Gyana within.

Gautama Buddha moves on to the first quality during the realization of Atma Gyana – seeing complete radiance of Atma Gyana everywhere.

Those who think they understand complete radiance actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes complete radiance, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 10 (Sanskrit):

शुभकृत्स्ने शुभकृत्स्नतः संजानाति ।
शुभकृत्स्ने शुभकृत्स्नतः संजात्वा
शुभकृत्स्ने मन्यते, शुभकृत्स्नेषु मन्यते, शुभकृत्स्नतः मन्यते, शुभकृत्स्ने मेति मन्यते,
शुभकृत्स्नम् अभिनन्दति ।
तत् कस्य हेतु ?
अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) complete goodness (Shubhakritsane) with respect to the (other) complete goodness (Shubhakritsanatha), having known (samgyaatva) complete goodness (Shubhakritsane) with respect to complete goodness (Shubhakritsanatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) complete goodness (Shubhakritsane), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in complete goodness (Shubhakritsaneshu), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from complete goodness (Shubhakritsanatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) complete goodness (Shubhakritsane),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the second form of realization) complete goodness (Shubhakritsanam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

शुभकृत्स्न = शुभ (auspicious, good) + कृत्स्न (all, complete, whole, entire, without remainder). Hence,

शुभकृत्स्न means complete goodness. The goal of Devas is to indulge only in completely good actions. These actions take them in the path of Atma Gyana.

Gautama Buddha moves on to the second quality during the realization of Atma Gyana – complete goodness.

Those who think they understand complete goodness actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but a inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside

and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes complete goodness, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 11 (Sanskrit):

बृहत्फले बृहत्फलतः संजानाति ।

बृहत्फले बृहत्फलतः संज्ञात्वा

बृहत्फले मन्यते, बृहत्फलेषु मन्यते, बृहत्फलतः मन्यते, बृहत्फले मेति मन्यते,

बृहत्फलम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the greatest fruit (Brihatphale) with respect to the (other) greatest fruit (Brihatphalatha), having known (samgyaatva) the greatest fruit (Brihatphale) with respect to the greatest fruit (Brihatphalatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the greatest fruit (Brihatphale), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the greatest fruit (Brihatphaleshu), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the greatest fruit (Brihatphalatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the greatest fruit (Brihatphale),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the third form of realization) the greatest fruit (Brihatphalam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

बृहत्फल is बृहत् (greatest) + फल (fruit). Brihatphale is used to denote a cosmic or universal scale. It is used only with respect to Vishnu, Prajapathi, Shiva etc.

Gautama Buddha moves on to the third quality during the realization of Atma Gyana – the greatest fruit.

Those who think they understand the greatest fruit actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside

and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the greatest fruit, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 12 (Sanskrit):

अभिभुं अभिभुतः संजानाति ।

अभिभुं अभिभुतः संज्ञात्वा

अभिभुं मन्यते, अभिभुस्मिन् मन्यते, अभिभुतः मन्यते, अभिभुं मेति मन्यते,

अभिभुम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the supreme manifestation (Abhibhum) with respect to the (other) supreme manifestation (Abhibhuthaha), having known (samgyaatva) the supreme manifestation (Abhibhum) with respect to the supreme manifestation (Abhibhuthaha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the supreme manifestation (Abhibhum), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the supreme manifestation (Abhibhusmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the supreme manifestation (Abhibhutaha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the supreme manifestation (Abhibhum),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the fourth form of realization) the supreme manifestation (Abhibhum).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

अभिभु is अभि (over) + √भू (become). Abhibhu is used to denote the supreme manifestation of the Brahman.

Gautama Buddha then moves on to the fourth quality during the realization of Atma Gyana – the supreme manifestation of the Brahman.

Those who think they understand the supreme manifestation actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside

and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the supreme manifestation, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 13 (Sanskrit):

आकाशानञ्चायतनम् आकाशानञ्चायतनतः संजानाति ।
आकाशानञ्चायतनम् आकाशानञ्चायतनतः संज्ञात्वा
आकाशानञ्चायतनम् मन्यते, आकाशानञ्चायतनस्मिन् मन्यते, आकाशानञ्चायतनतः मन्यते,
आकाशानञ्चायतनम् मेति मन्यते,
आकाशानञ्चायतनम् अभिनन्दति ।
तत् कस्य हेतु ?
अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanam) with respect to the (other) altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanatha), having known (samgyaatva) the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanam) with respect to the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the first form of realization) the altar of the infinite sky (Akasha anantha ayathanam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

आकाशानञ्चायतनम् is आकाश (sky) + आनन्त्य (endless, infinite) + आयतनम् (abode, altar).

Gautama Buddha moves on to the first abode during the realization of Atma Gyana – the altar of the infinite sky

Those who think they understand the altar of the infinite sky actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the altar of the infinite sky, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 14 (Sanskrit):

विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् विज्ञानानञ्चायतनतः संजानाति ।
विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् विज्ञानानञ्चायतनतः संज्ञात्वा
विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् मन्यते, विज्ञानानञ्चायतनस्मिन् मन्यते, विज्ञानानञ्चायतनतः मन्यते,
विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् मेति मन्यते,
विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् अभिनन्दति ।
तत् कस्य हेतु ?
अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanam) with respect to the (other) altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanatha), having known (samgyaatva) the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanam) with respect to the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the second form of realization) the altar of infinite knowledge (Vigyana anantha ayathanam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् is विज्ञान (knowledge) + आनन्त्य (endless, infinite) + आयतनम् (abode, altar).

Gautama Buddha moves on to the second abode during the realization of Atma Gyana – the altar of infinite knowledge

Those who think they understand the altar of infinite knowledge actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the altar of infinite knowledge, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 15 (Sanskrit):

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् आकिञ्चन्यायतनतः संजानाति ।

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् आकिञ्चन्यायतनतः संज्ञात्वा

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् मन्यते, आकिञ्चन्यायतनस्मिन् मन्यते, आकिञ्चन्यायतनतः मन्यते,

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् मेति मन्यते,

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanam) with respect to the (other) altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanatha), having known (samgyaatva) the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanam) with respect to the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the third form of realization) the altar of not-anything (Akinchana ayathanam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् is आकिञ्चन्य (not anything, nothing) + आयतनम् (abode, altar).

Gautama Buddha moves on to the third abode during the realization of Atma Gyana – the altar of not-anything

Those who think they understand the altar of not-anything actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the altar of not-anything, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 16 (Sanskrit):

नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनतः संज्ञानाति ।

नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनतः संज्ञात्वा

नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् मन्यते, नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनस्मिन् मन्यते, नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनतः

मन्यते, नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् मेति मन्यते,

नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanam) with respect to the (other) altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanatha), having known (samgyaatva) the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanam) with respect to the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Akinchana ayathanatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanatha), understands (manyathe) one’s

identification with (methi) the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the fourth form of realization) the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” (Naiva samjna na samajna ayathanam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् is नैव (Neither) + संज्ञा (understanding) + न (not) + असंज्ञा (not understanding) + आयतनम् (abode, altar).

Gautama Buddha then moves on to the fourth abode during the realization of Atma Gyana – the altar of “neither understanding or non-understanding.”

Those who think they understand the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding” actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the altar of “neither understanding nor non-understanding,” not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 17 (Sanskrit):

दृष्टं दृष्टतः संजानाति ।

दृष्टं दृष्टतः संज्ञात्वा

दृष्टं मन्यते, दृष्टस्मिन् मन्यते, दृष्टतः मन्यते, दृष्टं मेति मन्यते,

दृष्टम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) sight (Dristam) with respect to the (other) sight (Drishtatha), having known (samgyaatva) sight (Dristam) with respect to sight (Drishtatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) sight (Dristam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in sight (Dristasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from sight (Drishtatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) sight (Dristam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the first form of realization) sight (Dristam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the first sense during the realization of Atma Gyana – Dristam or sight. One sees the visible world and recognizes the living beings within.

Those who think they understand sight actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes sight, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 18 (Sanskrit):

श्रुतं श्रुततः संजानाति ।

श्रुतं श्रुततः संज्ञात्वा

श्रुतं मन्यते, श्रुतस्मिन् मन्यते, श्रुततः मन्यते, श्रुतं मेति मन्यते,

श्रुतम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) sight (Shrutham) with respect to the (other) sight (Shrutatha), having known (samgyaatva) sight (Shrutham) with respect to sight (Shrutatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) sight (Shrutham), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in sight (Shruthasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from sight (Shrutatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) sight (Shrutham),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the second form of realization) sight (Shrutham).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the second sense during the realization of Atma Gyana – Shrutham or hearing. One learns about the Devas through the Shrutis (Vedas).

Those who think they understand hearing actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes hearing, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 19 (Sanskrit):

मतं मततः संजानाति ।

मतं मततः संज्ञात्वा

मतं मन्यते, मतस्मिन् मन्यते, मततः मन्यते, मतं मेति मन्यते,

मतम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) understanding (Matham) with respect to the (other) understanding (Matatha), having known (samgyaatva) understanding (Matham) with respect to understanding (Matatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) understanding (Matham), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in understanding (Mathasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from understanding (Matatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) understanding (Matham),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the third form of realization) understanding (Matham).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the third sense during the realization of Atma Gyana – Matham or understanding. One learns about Prajapathi Brahma through understanding deeply the Shrutis (Vedas).

Those who think they understand “understanding” actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes “understanding,” not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 20 (Sanskrit):

विज्ञातं विज्ञाततः संजानाति ।

विज्ञातं विज्ञाततः संज्ञात्वा

विज्ञातं मन्यते, विज्ञातस्मिन् मन्यते, विज्ञाततः मन्यते, विज्ञातं मेति मन्यते,

विज्ञातम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) higher knowledge (Vigyatham) with respect to the (other) higher knowledge (Vigyatatha), having known (samgyaatva) higher knowledge (Matham) with respect to higher knowledge (Vigyatatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) higher knowledge (Vigyatham), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in higher knowledge (Vigyathasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from higher knowledge (Vigyatatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) higher knowledge (Vigyatham),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the fourth form of realization) higher knowledge. (Vigyatham)

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha then moves on to the fourth sense during the realization of Atma Gyana – Vigyatham or “higher knowledge.” One learns about the Brahman through the highest knowledge of the Shrutis (Vedas).

Those who think they understand “higher knowledge” actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes “higher knowledge,” not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 21 (Sanskrit):

एकत्वम् एकत्वतः संजानाति ।

एकत्वम् एकत्वतः संजात्वा

एकत्वम् मन्यते, एकत्वस्मिन् मन्यते, एकत्वतः मन्यते, एकत्वम् मेति मन्यते,

एकत्वम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the ego (Ekatvam) with respect to the (other) ego (Ekatvatha), having known (samgyaatva) the ego (Ekatvam) with respect to the ego (Ekatvatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the ego (Ekatvam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the ego (Ekatvasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the ego (Ekatvatha), understands (manyathe) one’s identification with (methi) the ego (Ekatvam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the first form of realization) the ego (Ekatvam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the first essence of the realization of Atma Gyana – Ekatvam or the knowledge of the singular. Here, this knowledge is of “the ego,” which tries to subordinate the universe.

Those who think they understand the ego actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes the ego, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 22 (Sanskrit):

नानात्वम् नानात्वतः संजानाति ।

नानात्वम् नानात्वतः संज्ञात्वा

नानात्वम् मन्यते, नानात्वस्मिन् मन्यते, नानात्वतः मन्यते, नानात्वम् मेति मन्यते,

नानात्वम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) the many (Nanathvam) with respect to the (other) many (Nanathvatha), having known (samgyaatva) the many (Nanathvam) with respect to the many (Nanathvatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) the many (Nanathvam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in the many (Nanathvasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from the many (Nanathvatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) the many (Nanathvam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the second form of realization) the many (Nanathvam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the second essence of the realization of Atma Gyana – Nanathvam or the knowledge of the many. Here, this knowledge is of “the many.”

Those who think they understand “the many” actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside

and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes “the many,” not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 23 (Sanskrit):

सर्वं सर्वतः संजानाति ।

सर्वं सर्वतः संज्ञात्वा

सर्वं मन्यते, सर्वस्मिन् मन्यते, सर्वतः मन्यते, सर्वं मेति मन्यते,

सर्वम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) all (Sarvam) with respect to the (other) all (Sarvatha), having known (samgyaatva) all (Sarvam) with respect to all (Sarvatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) all (Sarvam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in all (Sarvasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from all (Sarvatha), understands (manyathe) one’s identification with (methi) all (Sarvam),

(He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the third form of realization) all (Sarvam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha moves on to the third essence of the realization of Atma Gyana – Sarvam or the knowledge of all. Here, this knowledge is all living and non-living beings.

Those who think they understand “all” actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes “all,” not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 24 (Sanskrit):

निर्वाणं निर्वाणतः संजानाति ।

निर्वाणं निर्वाणतः संज्ञात्वा

निर्वाणं मन्यते, निर्वाणस्मिन् मन्यते, निर्वाणतः मन्यते, निर्वाणं मेति मन्यते,

निर्वाणम् अभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

अपरिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

(He) understands (samjaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) with respect to the (other) Nirvana (Nirvanatha), having known (samgyaatva) Nirvana (Nirvanam) with respect to Nirvana (Nirvanatha),

(He) understands (manyathe) Nirvana (Nirvanam), understands (manyathe) (the constituents) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), understands (manyathe) (the manifestations) from Nirvana (Nirvanatha), understands (manyathe) one's identification with (methi) Nirvana (Nirvanam), (He) rejoices (abhinandathi) in (the fourth form of realization) Nirvana (Nirvanam).

What (kasya) causes (hetu) that (tath)?

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) that (tasya) is not completely (apari) understood (gyaatham) (by the knower).

Commentary:

Gautama Buddha then moves on to the fourth essence of the realization of Atma Gyana – Nirvana or complete cessation.

Those who think they understand Nirvana actually understand not the outer manifestation of that entity, but an inner construct of that object. Unknowingly, they understand the outside entity as a projection of the inner mental construct.

The fool thinks they understand the perceived outer element, but in fact only knows the mental construct of the same. He merely experiences a mental construct in the world outside and thinks that the construct belongs to the outside world. The transformations are unbelievable and magical.

This foolish person rejoices about life in a universe which includes Nirvana, not understanding that he is merely living in a false mental construct projected outside.

What causes this mistake? It is a false understanding of what reality represents. The observer has no idea of the truth.

Verse 25 (Sanskrit):

पृथग्जनवशेन प्रथमनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

योऽपि स, भिक्षवः, भिक्षुः शैक्षः अप्राप्तमानसः अनुत्तरं योगक्षेमं प्रार्थयमानो विहरति,

सोऽपि पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजानाति; पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजाय पृथिवीं मा मन्यीत, पृथिव्यां

मा मन्यीत, पृथिवीतः मा मन्यीत, पृथिवीं मेति मा मन्यीत, पृथिवीं माभिनन्दीत ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

परिज्ञेय्यं तस्येति वदामि ।

आपम् ...पे... तेजम् ... वायम् ... भूतानि ... देवान् ... प्रजापतिम् ... ब्रह्मम् ... आभास्वरान् ...
बृहत्फलान् ... अभिभुम् ... आकाशानञ्चायतनम् ... विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् ... आकिञ्चन्यायतनम्
... नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् ... दृष्टम् ... श्रुतम् ... मतम् ... विज्ञातम् ... एकत्वम् ... नानात्वम् ...
सर्वम् ... निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिजानाति; निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिज्ञाय निर्वाणम् मा मन्यीत,
निर्वाणस्मिन् मा मन्यीत, निर्वाणतः मा मन्यीत, निर्वाणम् मेति मा मन्यीत, निर्वाणम्
माभिनन्दीत ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

परिज्ञेय्यं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the lay (prithak) man (jan), the first (pratham) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi)

O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), even (api) that (sa) trainee (shaiksha) Bhikshu, one whose mind (maanasa) has not attained (apraapth) excellent (anutharam) yoga and prosperity (kshema); he (sa), desiring (praarthayamaan), dwells (viharthi) also (api).

On earth (Prithveem); even (api) that (sa) (he) directly (abhi) knows (jaanati) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); having directly (abhi) known (gyaay) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); (he) should not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "in earth" (Prithvyaam), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "from earth" (Prithveetha), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) as "mine" (me); thus (iti) (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) (and) not (maa) delight (abhinandeeth) (in it)

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Thus (iti) I say (vadaami) (so) to be completely (pari) understood (ghyeyam) by him (tasya).

- divine waters (Aapam)...Fire (Tejam)...Air (Vaayam)...
- living creatures (Bhuthani)...Devas...Prajapathi Brahma...Brahman...
- complete radiance (aabasvar)...complete goodness (shubhkritsn)...greatest fruit (bhihatphala)...supreme manifestation (abhibhu)...
- altar (ayatanam) of the infinite (ananta) sky (Akasha)...altar (ayatanam) of infinite (ananta) knowledge (vijyana)...altar (ayatanam) of not anything (akinchana)...altar (ayatanam) of understanding (samjna) and not understanding (asamjna)
- sight (drishtam)...hearing (shrutham)...understanding (matham)...higher knowledge (vigyatham)
- singularity of the ego (ekatvam)...the many (nanathvam)...all (sarvam)...Nirvana

(He) directly (abhi) knows (jaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); having directly known (abhygyay) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana (Nirvanam) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) (of Nirvana) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana as "mine" (me); thus (iti) not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of delighting (abhinandeeth) in Nirvana.

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Thus (iti) I say (vadaami) (so) to be completely (pari) understood (ghyeyam) by him (tasya).

Commentary:

The first exposition is for the layman - the trainee Bhikshu

His mind is not perfect as it desires and dwells

He should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of earth without relating to it. He should not think of it as belonging to him in any way. Only then can he properly understand the earth.

He should then similarly investigate the 3 Panchabhutas, 4 denizens, 4 qualities, 4 abodes, 4 senses and 4 essences.

Finally, he should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of Nirvana without relating to it. Only then can he properly understand Nirvana.

Verse 26 (Sanskrit):

शैक्षवशेन द्वितीयनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

योऽपि स, भिक्षवः, भिक्षुः अर्हन् क्षीणास्रवः उषितवान् कृतकरणीयः ओहितभारः अनुप्राप्तस्वार्थः

परिक्षीणभवसंयोजनः सम्यगाज्ञाविमुक्तः,

सोऽपि पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजानाति; पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजाय पृथिवीं न मन्यते, पृथिव्यां न मन्यते, पृथिवीतः न मन्यते, पृथिवीं मेति न मन्यते, पृथिवीं नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

परिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

आपम् ...पे... तेजम् ... वायम् ... भूतानि ... देवान् ... प्रजापतिम् ... ब्रह्मम् ... आभास्वरान् ...

शुभकृत्स्नान् ... बृहत्फलान् ... अभिभुम् ... आकाशानञ्चायतनम् ... विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् ...

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् ... नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् ... दृष्टम् ... श्रुतम् ... मतम् ... विज्ञातम् ...

एकत्वम् ... नानात्वम् ... सर्वम् ... निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिजानाति; निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः

अभिजाय निर्वाणम् न मन्यते, निर्वाणस्मिन् न मन्यते, निर्वाणतः न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् मेति न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

परिज्ञातं तस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the trainee (shaiksha), the second (dvithiya) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi)

O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), even (api) that (sa) Arhat Bhikshu, who (yaha) has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), has lived (uchithvaan) (well). (He is) one who done (karneeya) work (kritha), laid down (ohith) baara (burden), following which (anu) has attained (praaptha) his own (sva) goals (artha), destroyed (pariksheen) the manifested (bhava)

yoke (samyojan), liberating (vimukth) himself with the correct (Samyak) and higher knowledge (aagya).

On earth (Prithveem); even (api) that (sa) (he) directly (abhi) knows (jaanati) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); having directly (abhi) known (gyaay) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); (he) should not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "in earth" (Prithvyaam), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "from earth" (Prithveetha), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) as "mine" (me); thus (iti) (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) (and) not (maa) delight (abhinandeeth) (in it)

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Thus (iti) I say (vadaami) (so) to be completely (pari) understood (ghyeyam) by him (tasya).

- divine waters (Aapam)...Fire (Tejam)...Air (Vaayam)...
- living creatures (Bhuthani)...Devas...Prajapathi Brahma...Brahman...
- complete radiance (aabasvar)...complete goodness (shubhkritsn)...greatest fruit (bhihatphala)...supreme manifestation (abhibhu)...
- altar (ayatanam) of the infinite (ananta) sky (Akasha)...altar (ayatanam) of infinite (ananta) knowledge (vijyana)...altar (ayatanam) of not anything (akinchana)...altar (ayatanam) of understanding (samjna) and not understanding (asamjna)
- sight (drishtam)...hearing (shrutham)...understanding (matham)...higher knowledge (vivyatham)
- singularity of the ego (ekatvam)...the many (nanathvam)...all (sarvam)...Nirvana

(He) directly (abhi) knows (jaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); having directly known (abhigay) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana (Nirvanam) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) (of Nirvana) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana as "mine" (me); thus (iti) not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of delighting (abhinandeeth) in Nirvana.

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Thus (iti) I say (vadaami) (so) to be completely (pari) understood (ghyeyam) by him (tasya).

Commentary:

The second exposition is for the layman - the trainee Bhikshu

Like the Arhat, he has to destroy his afflictions, burdens, yokes and liberate himself with higher knowledge.

He should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of earth without relating to it. He should not think of it as belonging to him in any way. Only then can he properly understand the earth.

He should then similarly investigate the 3 Panchabhutas, 4 denizens, 4 qualities, 4 abodes, 4 senses and 4 essences.

Finally, he should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of Nirvana without relating to it. Only then can he properly understand Nirvana.

Verse 27 (Sanskrit):

क्षीणास्रववशेन तृतीयनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

योऽपि स, भिक्षुः, भिक्षुः अर्हन् क्षीणास्रवः उषितवान् कृतकरणीयः ओहितभारः अनुप्राप्तस्वार्थः
परिक्षीणभवसंयोजनः सम्यगाज्ञया विमुक्तः,

सोऽपि पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजानाति; पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजाय पृथिवीं न मन्यते, पृथिव्यां न
मन्यते, पृथिवीतः न मन्यते, पृथिवीं मेति न मन्यते, पृथिवीं नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

रागस्य क्षयात्, वीतरागत्वात् ।

आपम् ...पे... तेजम् ... वायम् ... भूतानि ... देवान् ... प्रजापतिम् ... ब्रह्मम् ... आभास्वरान् ...

शुभकृत्स्नान् ... बृहत्फलान् ... अभिभुम् ... आकाशानञ्चायतनम् ... विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् ...

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् ... नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् ... दृष्टम् ... श्रुतम् ... मतम् ... विज्ञातम् ...

एकत्वम् ... नानात्वम् ... सर्वम् ... निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिजानाति; निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः

अभिजाय निर्वाणम् न मन्यते, निर्वाणस्मिन् न मन्यते, निर्वाणतः न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् मेति न
मन्यते, निर्वाणम् नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

रागस्य क्षयात्, वीतरागत्वात् ।

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the one who has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), the third (thrithiya) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi)

O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), even (api) that (sa) Arhat Bhikshu, who (yaha) has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), has lived (uchithvaan) (well). (He is) one who done (karneeya) work (kritha), laid down (ohith) baara (burden), following which (anu) has attained (praaptha) his own (sva) goals (artha), destroyed (pariksheen) the manifested (bhava) yoke (samyojan), liberating (vimukth) himself with the correct (Samyak) and higher knowledge (aagyaa).

On earth (Prithveem); even (api) that (sa) (he) directly (abhi) knows (jaanati) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); having directly (abhi) known (gyaay) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); (he) should not (na) think (manyeth) of "in earth" (Prithvyaam), not (na) think (manyeth) of "from earth" (Prithveetha), not (na) think (manyeth) of earth (Prithveem) as "mine" (me); thus (iti) (he) should not (ma) think (manyeth) of earth (Prithveem) (and) not (maa) delight (abhinandeeth) (in it)

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

From destruction (kshayaath) of desire (raagasya), state of being (tva) devoid of (veeth) desire (raaga)

- divine waters (Aapam)...Fire (Tejam)...Air (Vaayam)...
- living creatures (Bhuthani)...Devas...Prajapathi Brahma...Brahman...

- complete radiance (aabasvar)...complete goodness (shubhkritsn)...greatest fruit (bhihatphala)...supreme manifestation (abhibhu)...
- altar (ayatanam) of the infinite (ananta) sky (Akasha)...altar (ayatanam) of infinite (ananta) knowledge (vijyana)...altar (ayatanam) of not anything (akinchana)...altar (ayatanam) of understanding (samjna) and not understanding (asamjna)
- sight (drishtam)...hearing (shrutham)...understanding (matham)...higher knowledge (vigyatham)
- singularity of the ego (ekatvam)...the many (nanathvam)...all (sarvam)...Nirvana

(He) directly (abhi) knows (jaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); having directly known (abhigyay) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); (he) should not (ma) think (manyeetha) of Nirvana (Nirvanam) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), not (ma) think (manyeetha) (of Nirvana) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha), not (ma) think (manyeetha) of Nirvana as "mine" (me); thus (iti) not (ma) think (manyeetha) of delighting (abhinandeeth) in Nirvana.

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

From destruction (kshayaath) of desire (raagasya), state of being (tva) devoid of (veeth) desire (raaga).

Commentary:

The third exposition is for the one who has destroyed his afflictions

Like the Arhat, he has to destroy his afflictions, burdens, yokes and liberate himself with higher knowledge.

He should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of earth without relating to it. He should not think of it as belonging to him in any way. Only then can he properly understand the earth.

He should then similarly investigate the 3 Panchabhutas, 4 denizens, 4 qualities, 4 abodes, 4 senses and 4 essences.

Finally, he should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of Nirvana without relating to it. Only then can he destroy the desires within.

Verse 28 (Sanskrit):

क्षीणास्रवशेन चतुर्थनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

योऽपि स, भिक्षवः, भिक्षुः अर्हन् क्षीणास्रवः उषितवान् कृतकरणीयः ओहितभारः अनुप्राप्तस्वार्थः
परिक्षीणभवसंयोजनः सम्यगाज्ञाविमुक्तः,

सोऽपि पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजानाति; पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिज्ञाय पृथिवीं न मन्यते, पृथिव्यां न मन्यते, पृथिवीतः न मन्यते, पृथिवीं मेति न मन्यते, पृथिवीं नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

दोषस्य क्षयात्, वीतदोषत्वात् ।

आपम् ...पे... तेजम् ... वायम् ... भूतानि ... देवान् ... प्रजापतिम् ... ब्रह्मम् ... आभास्वरान् ...

शुभकृत्स्नान् ... बृहत्फलान् ... अभिभुम् ... आकाशानञ्चायतनम् ... विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् ...

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् ... नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् ... दृष्टम् ... श्रुतम् ... मतम् ... विज्ञातम् ...

एकत्वम् ... नानात्वम् ... सर्वम् ... निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिजानाति; निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः
अभिजाय निर्वाणम् न मन्यते, निर्वाणस्मिन् न मन्यते, निर्वाणतः न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् मेति न
मन्यते, निर्वाणम् नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

दोषस्य क्षयात्, वीतदोषत्वात् ।

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the one has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), the fourth (Chaturtha) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi)

O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), even (api) that (sa) Arhat Bhikshu, who (yaha) has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), has lived (uchithvaan) (well). (He is) one who done (karneeya) work (kritha), laid down (ohith) baara (burden), following which (anu) has attained (praaptha) his own (sva) goals (artha), destroyed (pariksheen) the manifested (bhava) yoke (samyojan), liberating (vimukth) himself with the correct (Samyak) and higher knowledge (aagyaa).

On earth (Prithveem); even (api) that (sa) (he) directly (abhi) knows (jaanati) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); having directly (abhi) known (gyaay) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); (he) should not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "in earth" (Prithvyaam), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "from earth" (Prithveetha), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) as "mine" (me); thus (iti) (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) (and) not (maa) delight (abhinandeeth) (in it)

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

From destruction (kshayaath) of faults (dosha), state of being (tva) devoid of (veeth) faults (dosha)

- divine waters (Aapam)...Fire (Tejam)...Air (Vaayam)...
- living creatures (Bhuthani)...Devas...Prajapathi Brahma...Brahman...
- complete radiance (aabasvar)...complete goodness (shubhkritsn)...greatest fruit (bhihatphala)...supreme manifestation (abhibhu)...
- altar (ayatanam) of the infinite (ananta) sky (Akasha)...altar (ayatanam) of infinite (ananta) knowledge (vijyana)...altar (ayatanam) of not anything (akinchana)...altar (ayatanam) of understanding (samjna) and not understanding (asamjna)
- sight (drishtam)...hearing (shrutham)...understanding (matham)...higher knowledge (vigyatham)
- singularity of the ego (ekatvam)...the many (nanathvam)...all (sarvam)...Nirvana

(He) directly (abhi) knows (jaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); having directly known (abhygyay) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana (Nirvanam) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) (of Nirvana) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana as "mine" (me); thus (iti) not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of delighting (abhinandeeth) in Nirvana.

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

From destruction (kshayaath) of faults (dosha), state of being (tva) devoid of (veeth) faults (dosha).

Commentary:

The fourth exposition is for the one who has destroyed his afflictions

Like the Arhat, he has to destroy his afflictions, burdens, yokes and liberate himself with higher knowledge.

He should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of earth without relating to it. He should not think of it as belonging to him in any way. Only then can he properly understand the earth.

He should then similarly investigate the 3 Panchabhutas, 4 denizens, 4 qualities, 4 abodes, 4 senses and 4 essences.

Finally, he should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of Nirvana without relating to it. Only then can he destroy the faults within.

Verse 29 (Sanskrit):

क्षीणास्रववशेन पञ्चमनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

योऽपि स, भिक्षवः, भिक्षुः अर्हन् क्षीणास्रवः उषितवान् कृतकरणीयः ओहितभारः अनुप्राप्तस्वार्थः
परिक्षीणभवसंयोजनः सम्यगाज्ञाविमुक्तः,

सोऽपि पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजानाति; पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजाय पृथिवीं न मन्यते, पृथिव्यां न
मन्यते, पृथिवीतः न मन्यते, पृथिवीं मेति न मन्यते, पृथिवीं नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

मोहस्य क्षयात्, वीतमोहत्वात् ।

आपम् ...पे... तेजम् ... वायम् ... भूतानि ... देवान् ... प्रजापतिम् ... ब्रह्मम् ... आभास्वरान् ...

शुभकृत्स्नान् ... बृहत्फलान् ... अभिभुम् ... आकाशानञ्चायतनम् ... विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् ...

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् ... नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् ... दृष्टम् ... श्रुतम् ... मतम् ... विज्ञातम् ...

एकत्वम् ... नानात्वम् ... सर्वम् ... निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिजानाति; निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः

अभिजाय निर्वाणम् न मन्यते, निर्वाणस्मिन् न मन्यते, निर्वाणतः न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् मेति न
मन्यते, निर्वाणम् नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

मोहस्य क्षयात्, वीतमोहत्वात् ।

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the one who has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), the fifth (panchami) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi)

O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), even (api) that (sa) Arhat Bhikshu, who (yaha) has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), has lived (uchithvaan) (well). (He is) one who done (karneeya) work (kritha), laid down (ohith) baara (burden), following which (anu) has attained (praaptha) his own (sva) goals (artha), destroyed (pariksheen) the manifested (bhava)

yoke (samyojan), liberating (vimukth) himself with the correct (Samyak) and higher knowledge (aagyaa).

On earth (Prithveem); even (api) that (sa) (he) directly (abhi) knows (jaanati) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); having directly (abhi) known (gyaay) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); (he) should not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "in earth" (Prithvyaam), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "from earth" (Prithveetha), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) as "mine" (me); thus (iti) (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) (and) not (maa) delight (abhinandeeth) (in it)

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

From destruction (kshayaath) of lust (moha), state of being (tva) devoid of (veeth) lust (moha)

- divine waters (Aapam)...Fire (Tejam)...Air (Vaayam)...
- living creatures (Bhuthani)...Devas...Prajapathi Brahma...Brahman...
- complete radiance (aabasvar)...complete goodness (shubhkritsn)...greatest fruit (bhihatphala)...supreme manifestation (abhibhu)...
- altar (ayatanam) of the infinite (ananta) sky (Akasha)...altar (ayatanam) of infinite (ananta) knowledge (vijyana)...altar (ayatanam) of not anything (akinchana)...altar (ayatanam) of understanding (samjna) and not understanding (asamjna)
- sight (drishtam)...hearing (shrutham)...understanding (matham)...higher knowledge (vigyatham)
- singularity of the ego (ekatvam)...the many (nanathvam)...all (sarvam)...Nirvana

(He) directly (abhi) knows (jaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); having directly known (abhigyay) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana (Nirvanam) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) (of Nirvana) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha), not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana as "mine" (me); thus (iti) not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of delighting (abhinandeeth) in Nirvana.

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

From destruction (kshayaath) of lust (moha), state of being (tva) devoid of (veeth) lust (moha).

Commentary:

The fifth exposition is for the one who has destroyed his afflictions

Like the Arhat, he has to destroy his afflictions, burdens, yokes and liberate himself with higher knowledge.

He should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of earth without relating to it. He should not think of it as belonging to him in any way. Only then can he properly understand the earth.

He should then similarly investigate the 3 Panchabhutas, 4 denizens, 4 qualities, 4 abodes, 4 senses and 4 essences.

Finally, he should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of Nirvana without relating to it. Only then can he destroy the lusts within.

Verse 30 (Sanskrit):

क्षीणास्रववशेन षष्ठनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

तथागतोऽपि, भिक्षवः, अर्हन् सम्यक्सम्बुद्धः पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजानाति;

पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिज्ञाय पृथिवीं न मन्यते, पृथिव्यां न मन्यते, पृथिवीतः न मन्यते, पृथिवीं मेति न मन्यते, पृथिवीं नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

परिज्ञातान्तं तथागतस्येति वदामि ।

आपम् ...पे... तेजम् ... वायम् ... भूतानि ... देवान् ... प्रजापतिम् ... ब्रह्मम् ... आभास्वरान् ...

शुभकृत्स्नान् ... बृहत्फलान् ... अभिभुम् ... आकाशानञ्चायतनम् ... विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् ...

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् ... नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् ... दृष्टम् ... श्रुतम् ... मतम् ... विज्ञातम् ...

एकत्वम् ... नानात्वम् ... सर्वम् ... निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिजानाति; निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः

अभिज्ञाय निर्वाणम् न मन्यते, निर्वाणस्मिन् न मन्यते, निर्वाणतः न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् मेति न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

परिज्ञातान्तं तथागतस्येति वदामि ।

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the one has destroyed (sheena) his afflictions (aasrav), the sixth (shashti) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi)

O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), also (api) the Arhat (arhan), the Tathagatha and the perfectly (samyak) complete (sam) Buddha directly (abhi) perceive (jaanaathi) earth (Prithveem) as earth (prithveetha)

On earth (Prithveem); (he) directly (abhi) knows (jaanati) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); having directly (abhi) known (gyaay) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); (he) should not (na) think (manyeth) of "in earth" (Prithvyaam), not (na) think (manyeth) of "from earth" (Prithveetha), not (na) think (manyeth) of earth (Prithveem) as "mine" (me); thus (iti) (he) should not (ma) think (manyeth) of earth (Prithveem) (and) not (maa) delight (abhinandeeth) (in it)

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Having complete (pari) knowledge (gyaa) till the very end (antha) of the (asya) Tathagatha, thus (iti) I say (vadaami)

- divine waters (Aapam)...Fire (Tejam)...Air (Vaayam)...
- living creatures (Bhuthani)...Devas...Prajapathi Brahma...Brahman...
- complete radiance (aabasvar)...complete goodness (shubhkritsn)...greatest fruit (bhihatphala)...supreme manifestation (abhibhu)...

- altar (ayatanam) of the infinite (ananta) sky (Akasha)...altar (ayatanam) of infinite (ananta) knowledge (vijyana)...altar (ayatanam) of not anything (akinchana)...altar (ayatanam) of understanding (samjna) and not understanding (asamjna)
- sight (drishtam)...hearing (shrutham)...understanding (matham)...higher knowledge (vigyatham)
- singularity of the ego (ekatvam)...the many (nanathvam)...all (sarvam)...Nirvana

(He) directly (abhi) knows (jaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); having directly known (abhigyay) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); (he) should not (ma) think (manyeetha) of Nirvana (Nirvanam) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), not (ma) think (manyeetha) (of Nirvana) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha), not (ma) think (manyeetha) of Nirvana as "mine" (me); thus (iti) not (ma) think (manyeetha) of delighting (abhinandeeth) in Nirvana.

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Having complete (pari) knowledge (gyaa) till the very end (antha) of the (asya) Tathagatha, thus (iti) I say (vadaami).

Commentary:

The sixth exposition is for the one who has destroyed his afflictions

The Arhat, Tathagatha and the Perfect Buddha, see earth as truly what is - earth.

He should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of earth without relating to it. He should not think of it as belonging to him in any way. Only then can he properly understand the earth.

He should then similarly investigate the 3 Panchabhutas, 4 denizens, 4 qualities, 4 abodes, 4 senses and 4 essences.

Finally, he should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of Nirvana without relating to it. Only then can he attain the complete and timeless knowledge of the Tathagatha.

Verse 31 (Sanskrit):

तथागतवशेन सप्तमनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

तथागतोऽपि, भिक्षवः, अर्हन् सम्यक्सम्बुद्धः

पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजानाति; पृथिवीं पृथिवीतः अभिजाय पृथिवीं न मन्यते, पृथिव्यां न मन्यते, पृथिवीतः न मन्यते, पृथिवीं मेति न मन्यते, पृथिवीं नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

“नन्दी दुःखस्य मूलम्” इति विदित्वा “भवात् जातिः भूतस्य जरामरणम्” इति ।

तस्मादिह, भिक्षवः, “तथागतः सर्वशः तृष्णानां क्षयात् विरागात् निरोधात् त्यागात् प्रतिसर्गात् अनुत्तरां सम्यक्सम्बोधिम् अभिसम्बुद्धः” इति वदामि ।

आपम् ...पे... तेजम् ... वायम् ... भूतानि ... देवान् ... प्रजापतिम् ... ब्रह्मम् ... आभास्वरान् ...

शुभकृत्स्नान् ... बृहत्फलान् ... अभिभुम् ... आकाशानञ्चायतनम् ... विज्ञानानञ्चायतनम् ...

आकिञ्चन्यायतनम् ... नैवसंज्ञानासंज्ञायतनम् ... दृष्टम् ... श्रुतम् ... मतम् ... विज्ञातम् ...

एकत्वम् ... नानात्वम् ... सर्वम् ... निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः अभिजानाति; निर्वाणम् निर्वाणतः

अभिजाय निर्वाणम् न मन्यते, निर्वाणस्मिन् न मन्यते, निर्वाणतः न मन्यते, निर्वाणम् मेति न

मन्यते, निर्वाणम् नाभिनन्दति ।

तत् कस्य हेतु ?

“नन्दी दुःखस्य मूलम्” इति विदित्वा “भवात् जातिः भूतस्य जरामरणम्” इति ।

तस्मादिह, भिक्षवः, “तथागतः सर्वशः तृष्णानां क्षयात् विरागात् निरोधात् त्यागात् प्रतिसर्गात् अनुत्तरां सम्यक्सम्बोधिम् अभिसम्बुद्धः” इति वदामि ॥

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the Tathagatha, the seventh (sapthami) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi)

O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), also (api) the Arhat (arhan), the Tathagatha and the perfectly (samyak) complete (sam) Buddha directly (abhi) perceive (jaanaathi) earth (Prithveem) as earth (prithveetha)

On earth (Prithveem); (he) directly (abhi) knows (jaanati) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); having directly (abhi) known (gyaay) earth (Prithveem) as earth (Prithveetha); (he) should not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "in earth" (Prithvyaam), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of "from earth" (Prithveetha), not (na) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) as "mine" (me); thus (iti) (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeeth) of earth (Prithveem) (and) not (maa) delight (abhinandeeth) (in it)

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Thus (iti), the root (mulam) of suffering (dukhasya) is (attachment to) happiness (nandi), thus (iti) having known (vidithva) birth (jaathi) of the living being (bhutasya) as the manifestation (bhavaath) of old age (jara) and death (maran)

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) - O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), therefore (tasmath) in this manner (iha), The Tathagatha (has) in every respect (sarvesh), through destruction (kshayaath), through dispassion (viraag), through restraint (nirodhaath, through sacrifice (thyagaath) (and) through relinquishment (prathisargaath) of cravings (trishnanaam), (by) the unsurpassed (anuttharaam), full (samyak) and complete (sam) awakening (bodhim) into (abhi) the perfect (sam) Buddha.

- divine waters (Aapam)...Fire (Tejam)...Air (Vaayam)...
- living creatures (Bhuthani)...Devas...Prajapathi Brahma...Brahman...
- complete radiance (aabasvar)...complete goodness (shubhkritsn)...greatest fruit (bhihatphala)...supreme manifestation (abhibhu)...
- altar (ayatanam) of the infinite (ananta) sky (Akasha)...altar (ayatanam) of infinite (ananta) knowledge (vijyana)...altar (ayatanam) of not anything (akinchana)...altar (ayatanam) of understanding (samjna) and not understanding (asamjna)
- sight (drishtam)...hearing (shrutham)...understanding (matham)...higher knowledge (vigyatham)
- singularity of the ego (ekatvam)...the many (nanathvam)...all (sarvam)...Nirvana

(He) directly (abhi) knows (jaanaathi) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); having directly known (abhigyay) Nirvana (Nirvanam) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha); (he) should not (ma) think (manyeeetha) of Nirvana (Nirvanam) in Nirvana (Nirvanasmin), not (ma) think

(manyeetha) (of Nirvana) as Nirvana (Nirvanatha), not (ma) think (manyeetha) of Nirvana as "mine" (me); thus (iti) not (ma) think (manyeetha) of delighting (abhinandeeth) in Nirvana.

What (kasya) is the cause (hethu) of that (that)?

Thus (iti), the root (mulam) of suffering (dukhasya) is (attachment to) happiness (nandi), thus (iti) having known (vidithva) birth (jaathi) of the living being (bhutasya) as the manifestation (bhavaath) of old age (jara) and death (maran)

Thus (iti), I say (vadaami) - O Bhikshus (Bhikshava), therefore (tasmath) in this manner (iha), The Tathagatha (has) in every respect (sarvesh), through destruction (kshayaath), through dispassion (viraag), through restraint (nirodhaath, through sacrifice (thyagaath) (and) through relinquishment (prathisargaath) of cravings (trishnanaam), (by) the unsurpassed (anuttharaam), full (samyak) and complete (sam)awakening (bodhim) into (abhi) the perfect (sam) Buddha.

Commentary:

The seventh exposition is for the Tathagatha.

The Arhat, Tathagatha and the Perfect Buddha, see earth as truly what is - earth.

He should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of earth without relating to it. He should not think of it as belonging to him in any way. Only then can he properly understand the earth.

The root of suffering is the clinging to happiness. The beginning as birth is truly the beginning of death. By destruction, dispassion, restraint, sacrifice, relinquishment of cravings, the Tathagatha has attained the full and complete awakening as the perfect Buddha. He should then similarly investigate the 3 Panchabhutas, 4 denizens, 4 qualities, 4 abodes, 4 senses and 4 essences.

Finally, he should dispassionately and directly investigate the idea of Nirvana without relating to it. Only then can he attain the nature of the perfect Buddha.

Verse 32 (Sanskrit):

तथागतवशेन अष्टमनयभूमिपरिच्छेदो निष्ठितः ।

इदमवोच भगवान् । न ते भिक्षवः भगवतो भाषितम् अभिनन्दन् ।

मूलपर्यायसूत्रं निष्ठितम् । प्रथमम् ॥

English translation:

From the standpoint (vashena) of the Tathagatha, the eighth (ashtami) method (naya) of exposition (parichedh) is completed (nishtith) on the ground (bhoomi).

This (idam) Bhagavan spoke (avoch). They (te), the Bhikshus (bhikshava) of the Bhagavan (bhagavatha) applauded (abhinandan) not (na) the discourse (bhaashitham).

The Mulaparyayasutram is completed (nishtitham); for the first time (prathamam).

Commentary:

Thus, the Mulaparyayasutram is completed. The Bhikshus, many of whom were mindless Sanathana Hindu ritualists, were upset with the message.

The Buddha was portraying the true message of Vedic Hindu thought that was very uncomfortable for the ritualists. Looking within and destroying the impurities within was a tall order for the ritualists.

References:

SuttaCentral. (n.d.). *Mūlapariyāyasutta—Mahāsaṅgīti Tipiṭaka Buddhavasse 2500*. Retrieved May 15, 2026, from [https://suttacentral.net/mn1/pli/ms?lang=en&layout=sidebyside&reference=none¬es=side notes&highlight=true&script=RomanReadable](https://suttacentral.net/mn1/pli/ms?lang=en&layout=sidebyside&reference=none¬es=side%20notes&highlight=true&script=RomanReadable)

Appendix 1: Complete Moolapariyayasutta Sutta in Anglicized Pali (from Suttacentral)

Introduction:

evam' me sutam'— ekam' समयam' bhagavaa ukkat't'haayam' viharati subhagavane saalaraaj amoole. tatra kho bhagavaa bhikkhoo aamantesi: “bhikkhavo”ti.

“bhadante”ti te bhikkhoo bhagavato pachchassosum'. bhagavaa etadavocha:

“sabbadhammoolapariyaayam' vo, bhikkhave, desessaami. tam' sunaatha, saadhukam' man asi karotha, bhaasissaamee”ti.

“evam', bhante”ti kho te bhikkhoo bhagavato pachchassosum'. bhagavaa etadavocha:

Verse 1 “idha, bhikkhave, assutavaa puthujjano ariyaanam' adassaavee ariyadhammassa akovido ariyadhamme avineeto, sappurisaanam' adassaavee sappurisdhammassa akovido sappurisdhamme avineeto—

pathavim' pathavito sanjaanaati; pathavim' pathavito sannatvaa pathavim' mannyati, pathaviyaa mannyati, pathavito mannyati, pathavim' meti mannyati, pathavim' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 2 aapam' aapato sanjaanaati; aapam' aapato sannatvaa aapam' mannyati, aapasmim' mannyati, aapato mannyati, aapam' meti mannyati, aapam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 3 tejam' tejato sanjaanaati; tejam' tejato sannatvaa tejam' mannyati, tejasim' mannyati, tejato mannyati, tejam' meti mannyati, tejam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 4 vaayam' vaayato sanjaanaati; vaayam' vaayato sannatvaa vaayam' mannyati, vaayasmim' mannyati, vaayato mannyati, vaayam' meti mannyati, vaayam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 5 bhoote bhootato sanjaanaati; bhoote bhootato sannatvaa bhoote mannyati, bhootesu mannyati, bhootato mannyati, bhoote meti mannyati, bhoote abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 6 deve devato sanjaanaati; deve devato sannatvaa deve mannyati, devesu mannyati, devato mannyati, deve meti mannyati, deve abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 7 pajaapatim' pajaapatito sanjaanaati; pajaapatim' pajaapatito sannatvaa pajaapatim' mannyati, pajaapatismim' mannyati, pajaapatito mannyati, pajaapatim' meti mannyati, pajaapatim' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 8 brahmam' brahmato sanjaanaati; brahmam' brahmato sannatvaa brahmam' mannyati, brahmasim' mannyati, brahmato mannyati, brahmam' meti mannyati, brahmam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 9 aabhassare aabhassarato sanjaanaati; aabhassare aabhassarato sannatvaa aabhassare mannyati, aabhassaresu mannyati, aabhassarato mannyati, aabhassare meti mannyati, aabhassare abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? ‘aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 10 subhakinhe subhakinhato sanjaanaati; subhakinhe subhakinhato sannyatvaa subhakinhe mannyati, subhakinhesu mannyati, subhakinhato mannyati, subhakinhe meti mannyati, subhakinhe abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 11 vehapphale vehapphalato sanjaanaati; vehapphale vehapphalato sannyatvaa vehapphale mannyati, vehapphalesu mannyati, vehapphalato mannyati, vehapphale meti mannyati, vehapphale abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 12 abhibhum' abhibhuto sanjaanaati; abhibhum' abhibhuto sannyatvaa abhibhum' mannyati, abhibhusmim' mannyati, abhibhuto mannyati, abhibhum' meti mannyati, abhibhum' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 13 aakaasaananchaayatanam' aakaasaananchaayatanato sanjaanaati; aakaasaananchaayatanam' aakaasaananchaayatanato sannyatvaa aakaasaananchaayatanam' mannyati, aakaasaananchaayatanasmim' mannyati, aakaasaananchaayatanato mannyati, aakaasaananchaayatanam' meti mannyati, aakaasaananchaayatanam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 14 vinnyaananchaayatanam' vinnyaananchaayatanato sanjaanaati; vinnyaananchaayatanam' vinnyaananchaayatanato sannyatvaa vinnyaananchaayatanam' mannyati, vinnyaananchaayatanasmim' mannyati, vinnyaananchaayatanato mannyati, vinnyaananchaayatanam' meti mannyati, vinnyaananchaayatanam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 15 aakinchannyaayatanam' aakinchannyaayatanato sanjaanaati; aakinchannyaayatanam' aakinchannyaayatanato sannyatvaa aakinchannyaayatanam' mannyati, aakinchannyaayatanasmim' mannyati, aakinchannyaayatanato mannyati, aakinchannyaayatanam' meti mannyati, aakinchannyaayatanam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 16 nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanato sanjaanaati; nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanato sannyatvaa nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' mannyati, nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanasmim' mannyati, nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanato mannyati, nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' meti mannyati, nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 17 dit't'ham' dit't'hato sanjaanaati; dit't'ham' dit't'hato sannyatvaa dit't'ham' mannyati, dit't'hasmim' mannyati, dit't'hato mannyati, dit't'ham' meti mannyati, dit't'ham' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 18 sutam' sutato sanjaanaati; sutam' sutato sannyatvaa sutam' mannyati, sutasmim' mannyati, sutato mannyati, sutam' meti mannyati, sutam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 19 mutam' mutato sanjaanaati; mutam' mutato sannyatvaa mutam' mannyati, mutasmim' mannyati, mutato mannyati, mutam' meti mannyati, mutam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 20 vinnyaatam' vinnyaatato sanjaanaati; vinnyaatam' vinnyaatato sannyatvaa vinnyaatam' mannyati, vinnyaatasmim' mannyati, vinnyaatato mannyati, vinnyaatam' meti mannyati, vinnyaatam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 21 ekattam' ekattato sanjaanaati; ekattam' ekattato sannyatvaa ekattam' mannyati, ekattasmim' mannyati, ekattato mannyati, ekattam' meti mannyati, ekattam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 22 naanattam' naanattato sanjaanaati; naanattam' naanattato sannyatvaa naanattam' mannyati, naanattasmim' mannyati, naanattato mannyati, naanattam' meti mannyati, naanattam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 23 sabbam' sabbato sanjaanaati; sabbam' sabbato sannyatvaa sabbam' mannyati, sabbasmim' mannyati, sabbato mannyati, sabbam' meti mannyati, sabbam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 24 nibbaanam' nibbaanato sanjaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato sannyatvaa nibbaanam' mannyati, nibbaanasmim' mannyati, nibbaanato mannyati, nibbaanam' meti mannyati, nibbaanam' abhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'aparinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 25

puthujjanavasena pat'hamanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

yopi so, bhikkhave, bhikkhu sekkho appattamaanaso anuttaram' yogakkhemam' pathayamaa no viharati, sopi pathavim' pathavito abhijaanaati; pathavim' pathavito abhinnyaaya pathavim' maa mannyati, pathaviyaa maa mannyati, pathavito maa mannyati, pathavim' meti maa mannyati, pathavim' maabhinandi. tam' kissa hetu? 'parinnyeyyam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

aapam' ...pe... tejam' ... vaayam' ... bhoote ... deve ... pajaapatim' ... brahmam' ... aabhass are ... subhakinhe ... vehapphale ... abhibhum' ... aakaasaananchaayatanam' ... vinnyaananc haayatanam' ... aakinchannyaayatanam' ... nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' ... dit't'ham' ... sutam' ... mutam' ... vinnyaatam' ... ekattam' ... naanattam' ... sabbam' ... nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhijaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhinnyaaya nibbaanam' maa mannyati, nibbaanasmim' maa mannyati, nibbaanato maa mannyati, nibbaanam' meti maa mannyati, nibbaanam' maabhinandi. tam' kissa hetu? 'parinnyeyyam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 26

sekkhavasena dutiyanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

yopi so, bhikkhave, bhikkhu araham' kheenaasavo vusitavaa katakaraneeyo ohitabhaaro anup pattasadattho parikkheenabhavasam'yojano sammadannyaavimutto, sopi pathavim' pathavito abhijaanaati; pathavim' pathavito abhinnyaaya pathavim' na mannyati, pathaviyaa na mannyati, pathavito na mannyati, pathavim' meti na mannyati, pathavim' naabhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'parinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

aapam' ...pe... tejam' ... vaayam' ... bhoote ... deve ... pajaapatim' ... brahmam' ... aabhass are ... subhakinhe ... vehapphale ... abhibhum' ... aakaasaananchaayatanam' ... vinnyaananc haayatanam' ... aakinchannyaayatanam' ... nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' ... dit't'ham' ... sutam' ... mutam' ... vinnyaatam' ... ekattam' ... naanattam' ... sabbam' ... nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhijaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhinnyaaya nibbaanam' na mannyati, nibbaanasmim' na mannyati, nibbaanato na mannyati, nibbaanam' meti na mannyati, nibbaanam' naabhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'parinnyaatam' tassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 27

kheenaasavavasena tatiyanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

yopi so, bhikkhave, bhikkhu araham' kheenaasavo vusitavaa katakaraneeyo ohitabhaaro anup pattasadattho parikkheenabhavasam'yojano sammadannya vimutto, sopi pathavim' pathavito abhijaanaati; pathavim' pathavito abhinnyaaya pathavim' na mannyati, pathaviyaa na mannyati, pathavito na mannyati, pathavim' meti na mannyati, pathavim' naabhinandati. tam' kissa he tu? khayaa raagassa, veetaraagattaa.

aapam' ...pe... tejam' ... vaayam' ... bhoote ... deve ... pajaapatim' ... brahmam' ... aabhass are ... subhakinhe ... vehapphale ... abhibhum' ... aakaasaananchaayatanam' ... vinnyaananc haayatanam' ... aakinchannyaayatanam' ... nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' ... dit't'ham' ... sutam' ... mutam' ... vinnyaatam' ... ekattam' ... naanattam' ... sabbam' ... nibbaanam' nibba anato abhijaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhinnyaaya nibbaanam' na mannyati, nibbaanasm im' na mannyati, nibbaanato na mannyati, nibbaanam' meti na mannyati, nibbaanam' naabhin andati. tam' kissa hetu? khayaa raagassa, veetaraagattaa.

Verse 28

kheenaasavavasena chatutthanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

yopi so, bhikkhave, bhikkhu araham' kheenaasavo vusitavaa katakaraneeyo ohitabhaaro anup pattasadattho parikkheenabhavasam'yojano sammadannyaavimutto, sopi pathavim' pathavito abhijaanaati; pathavim' pathavito abhinnyaaya pathavim' na mannyati, pathaviyaa na mannyati, pathavito na mannyati, pathavim' meti na mannyati, pathavim' naabhinandati. tam' kissa het u? khayaa dosassa, veetadosattaa.

aapam' ...pe... tejam' ... vaayam' ... bhoote ... deve ... pajaapatim' ... brahmam' ... aabhass are ... subhakinhe ... vehapphale ... abhibhum' ... aakaasaananchaayatanam' ... vinnyaananc haayatanam' ... aakinchannyaayatanam' ... nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' ... dit't'ham' ... sutam' ... mutam' ... vinnyaatam' ... ekattam' ... naanattam' ... sabbam' ... nibbaanam' nibba anato abhijaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhinnyaaya nibbaanam' na mannyati, nibbaanasm im' na mannyati, nibbaanato na mannyati, nibbaanam' meti na mannyati, nibbaanam' naabhin andati. tam' kissa hetu? khayaa dosassa, veetadosattaa.

Verse 29

kheenaasavavasena panchamanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

yopi so, bhikkhave, bhikkhu araham' kheenaasavo vusitavaa katakaraneeyo ohitabhaaro anup pattasadattho parikkheenabhavasam'yojano sammadannyaavimutto, sopi pathavim' pathavito abhijaanaati; pathavim' pathavito abhinnyaaya pathavim' na mannyati, pathaviyaa na mannyati, pathavito na mannyati, pathavim' meti na mannyati, pathavim' naabhinandati. tam' kissa het u? khayaa mohassa, veetamohattaa.

aapam' ...pe... tejam' ... vaayam' ... bhoote ... deve ... pajaapatim' ... brahmam' ... aabhass are ... subhakinhe ... vehapphale ... abhibhum' ... aakaasaananchaayatanam' ... vinnyaananc haayatanam' ... aakinchannyaayatanam' ... nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' ... dit't'ham' ... sutam' ... mutam' ... vinnyaatam' ... ekattam' ... naanattam' ... sabbam' ... nibbaanam' nibba anato abhijaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhinnyaaya nibbaanam' na mannyati, nibbaanasm im' na mannyati, nibbaanato na mannyati, nibbaanam' meti na mannyati, nibbaanam' naabhin andati. tam' kissa hetu? khayaa mohassa, veetamohattaa.

Verse 30

kheenaasavavasena chhat't'hanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

tathaagatopi, bhikkhave, araham' sammaasambuddho pathavim' pathavito abhijaanaati; pathavim' pathavito abhinnyaaya pathavim' na mannyati, pathaviyaa na mannyati, pathavito na mannyati, pathavim' meti na mannyati, pathavim' naabhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'parinnyaatant am' tathaagatassaa'ti vadaami.

aapam' ...pe... tejam' ... vaayam' ... bhoote ... deve ... pajaapatim' ... brahman' ... aabhass are ... subhakinhe ... vehapphale ... abhibhum' ... aakaasaananchaayatanam' ... vinnyaananc haayatanam' ... aakinchannyaayatanam' ... nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' ... dit't'ham' ... sutam' ... mutam' ... vinnyaatam' ... ekattam' ... naanattam' ... sabbam' ... nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhijaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhinnyaaya nibbaanam' na mannyati, nibbaanasmim' na mannyati, nibbaanato na mannyati, nibbaanam' meti na mannyati, nibbaanam' naabhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'parinnyaatantam' tathaagatassaa'ti vadaami.

Verse 31

tathaagatavasena sattamanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

tathaagatopi, bhikkhave, araham' sammaasambuddho pathavim' pathavito abhijaanaati; pathavim' pathavito abhinnyaaya pathavim' na mannyati, pathaviyaa na mannyati, pathavito na mannyati, pathavim' meti na mannyati, pathavim' naabhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'nandee dukkhassa moolan'ti iti viditvaa 'bhavaa jaati bhootassa jaraamaranan'ti. tasmaatiha, bhikkhave, 'tathaagato sabbaso tanhaanam' khayaa viraagaa nirodhaa chaagaa pat'inissaggaa anuttaram' sammaasambodhim' abhisambuddho'ti vadaami.

aapam' ...pe... tejam' ... vaayam' ... bhoote ... deve ... pajaapatim' ... brahman' ... aabhass are ... subhakinhe ... vehapphale ... abhibhum' ... aakaasaananchaayatanam' ... vinnyaananc haayatanam' ... aakinchannyaayatanam' ... nevasannyaanaasannyaayatanam' ... dit't'ham' ... sutam' ... mutam' ... vinnyaatam' ... ekattam' ... naanattam' ... sabbam' ... nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhijaanaati; nibbaanam' nibbaanato abhinnyaaya nibbaanam' na mannyati, nibbaanasmim' na mannyati, nibbaanato na mannyati, nibbaanam' meti na mannyati, nibbaanam' naabhinandati. tam' kissa hetu? 'nandee dukkhassa moolan'ti— iti viditvaa 'bhavaa jaati bhootassa jaraamaranan'ti. tasmaatiha, bhikkhave, 'tathaagato sabbaso tanhaanam' khayaa viraagaa nirodhaa chaagaa pat'inissaggaa anuttaram' sammaasambodhim' abhisambuddho'ti vadaamee'ti.

Verse 32

tathaagatavasena at't'hamanayabhoomiparichchedo nit't'hito.

idamavocha bhagavaa. na te bhikkhoo bhagavato bhaasitam' abhinandunti.

moolapariyaayasuttam' nit't'hitam' pat'hamam'.